

Structural and Conducting Studies on Manganese-, Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc- and Cadmium(II) Polychelates

A. S. ASWAR* and S. G. BHADANGE

Department of Chemistry, Amravati University, Amravati-444 602

Manuscript received 4 December 1995, revised 15 July 1996, accepted 3 September 1996

Chelates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have been prepared from bis(mercaptoacetamide)-*p*-phenylenediamine [BMAPD]. All the chelates are coloured amorphous solids and highly insoluble in water and common organic solvents. Thermogravimetric analysis has been carried out. Kinetic and thermodynamic parameters have also been evaluated by using thermal decomposition pattern. D.C. electrical conductivity study has also been carried out.

The interaction between metal ions and ligands may lead to the formation of polychelates in which the chelated metal ions are bridged by ligand molecules¹. The formation of macromolecular chain may be expected for a ligand with two chelating sites which, for steric reasons, cannot interact with the same metal ions². The present communication describes synthetic, structural and thermal aspects of the polychelates of bis(mercaptoacetamide)-*p*-phenylenediamine with bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Cd ions. It also describes the d.c. electrical conductivity studies of the above polychelates.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE POLYCHELATES

Compd.	Metal % :		σ $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	(Temp. K)	E_a eV
	Found / (Calcd.)				
BMAPD					
[Mn-BMAPD.2H ₂ O] _n	14.99 (15.69)	3.93×10^{-10} 2.189×10^{-9} 6.948×10^{-8}	(313) (373) (513)		0.735
[Co-BMAPD.2H ₂ O] _n	16.25 (16.66)	9.831×10^{-12} 4.336×10^{-11} 8.506×10^{-10}	(303) (373) (513)		0.497
[Ni-BMAPD.2H ₂ O] _n	16.30 (16.42)	8.87×10^{-12} 2.65×10^{-11} 2.00×10^{-9}	(303) (373) (513)		0.664
[[Cu-BMAPD].2H ₂ O] _n	17.50 (17.84)	5.135×10^{-9} 9.06×10^{-9} 1.895×10^{-9}	(312) (373) (512)		0.547
[[Zn-BMAPD].2H ₂ O] _n	18.28 (18.30)	5.75×10^{-12} 8.51×10^{-11} 7.94×10^{-9}	(303) (373) (520)		0.348
[[Cd-BMAPD].2H ₂ O] _n	27.69 (27.86)	4.234×10^{-12} 3.65×10^{-11} 1.75×10^{-10}	(303) (373) (518)		0.420

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Results and Discussion

All the chelates (Table 1) are coloured and amorphous solids, insoluble in water and in common organic solvents,

indicating their polymeric nature³. The analytical data suggest 1 : 1 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

Infrared spectra : Comparison of the ir spectra of the chelates and ligand reveals no significant difference, but they do show some changes in band position of certain functional groups. The ligand bands at 3 310 (NH) and 1 340 cm⁻¹ (C-N) show negative shift (10–15 cm⁻¹) in the polychelates, suggesting coordination via amide nitrogen atom⁴. The ligand band at 2 590 cm⁻¹ (SH)⁵ disappears in all the polychelates, indicating complexation by replacing proton from SH group of the ligand. The ligand band at 1 450 cm⁻¹ (S-CH₂) is found at lower frequency in the chelates, indicating the formation of metal sulphur bond by removing proton of SH group. The ligand band at 1 660 cm⁻¹ (C-O) remains unaltered in all the chelates, suggesting the absence of coordination through C=O⁶. The metal chelates show new bands at 500–560 (M-N) and 290–360 cm⁻¹ (M-S)⁷. All polychelates display broad band at 3 400–3 500 cm⁻¹ (OH of water molecules). The Mn^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polychelates exhibit weak sharp bands at around 850 and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (coordinated water), suggesting six-coordinated structure⁸.

Electronic spectra and magnetic study : The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Cu^{II} polychelate shows two bands at 15 200 and 17 800 cm⁻¹, in their normally expected region for square-planar complexes⁹. The third intense broad band at 23 000 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to charge transfer or intra-ligand transition¹⁰. The Cu^{II} chelate exhibits normal magnetic moment (1.87 B.M.) expected for square-planar geometry around the metal ion¹¹. The Ni^{II} chelate exhibits three bands at 9 615, 16 940 and 23 220 cm⁻¹ due to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively, in an octahedral field¹². The ν_2/ν_1 ratio for the chelate (1.76) occurs in the usual range (1.6–1.82) for octahedral Ni^{II} chelates¹³. In the present case, this ratio is little high, which is indicative of distortion¹¹. The electronic spectral parameters⁴ are : $Dq = 1 039 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 518 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.475$. Low values of the B and β suggest the appreciable amount of the metal-ligand covalent bonding. For the Ni^{II} chelate, tetragonal

splitting for the excited levels ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ has been observed. The split components for ${}^3T_{2g}(F)$ are observed near 9 615 and 10 416 cm^{-1} and that of ${}^3T_{1g}(F)$ located near 16 660 and 19 940 cm^{-1} respectively. The two stronger components of $T_{2g}(F)$ and $T_{1g}(F)$ terms are assigned to the transitions belonging to E_g level which manifest that the tetragonal distortion of the octahedron is through elongation along the four-fold axis and this clearly suggests that the ligand exerts a stronger ligand field in the chelate rings than the axial water molecules. From the maxima of the bands and using expression derived on the basis of crystal field approximations, the values of tetragonal parameters have been calculated: $Dt = 66 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $D_s = 460 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $Dq^{xy} = 1\,078 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $Dq^z = 980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The Ni^{II} polychelate has magnetic moment of 3.18 B.M. as expected for six-coordinated spin-free Ni^{II} species¹⁵. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of the Co^{II} polychelate exhibits a broad band around 9 040 cm^{-1} , assigned to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ transition. The two shoulders at ~19 260 and ~20 390 cm^{-1} probably on the tail of the charge transfer band have been observed. The former may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition and the latter to tetragonal distortion¹⁶. The electronic spectral parameters are¹⁷: $10 Dq = 10\,160 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B = 758 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.662$. The reduction of the Racah parameter (B) from the free-ion value of 971 cm^{-1} and β indicate the presence of strong covalence in the compound. The magnetic moment of the Co^{II} polychelate (4.93 B.M.) is close to the value required for octahedral structure. The Mn^{II} polychelate exhibits the transition sextet \rightarrow quartet. The ground term is ${}^6A_1(S)$ and exhibits three weak absorption maxima, the one at 14 340 cm^{-1} arising due to ${}^6A_1g \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(4G)$ transition, another at ~16 560 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^6A_1g \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(4G)$ and the third at ~20 000 cm^{-1} due to ${}^6A_1g \rightarrow {}^2E_g, {}^4A_1g(4G)$ for Mn^{II} ion in octahedral environment¹⁸. The magnetic moment (5.89 B.M.) of the complex indicates high-spin octahedral environment. The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} polychelates are found to be diamagnetic as expected for d^{10} ion system and may have tetrahedral geometry^{11,19}.

Thermal analysis: Thermal decomposition studies were made on ~10 mg samples. The polymeric metal chelates up to the decomposition point indicate that they are thermally stable. The presence of water molecule (lattice/coordinated) suggested from it is confirmed by TG analysis. According to Nikolaev *et al.*²⁰, water eliminated below 150° can be considered as lattice water and that eliminated above 150° may be due to its coordination to the metal atom present in chelates. In the present study, the weight losses of the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polychelates at 180–230° are 9.10 (10.03), 9.45 (9.70) and 8.08% (9.71%) respectively, the values in parenthesis corresponding to two coordinated water molecules per repeating unit of polychelate. The Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} polychelates show weight losses at 125–150° equal to 8.50 (9.48), 9.20 (10.02) and 8.40% (8.94%) respectively, the values in the parenthesis corresponding to two lattice water molecules. The TGA cur-

ves of all the polychelates attain stability around 600° and the weight of the residues correspond to the formation of the metal oxide. The order for thermal stability of polychelates is found to be: $\text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Cd} > \text{Cu} > \text{Zn}$. The thermal activation energy was calculated by employing the Freeman-Carroll equation²¹ and Sharp-Wentworth²² method. Further, various thermodynamic parameters have been calculated by using the data of Freeman-Carroll method and comparable values are summarised in Table 2. The similarity in values of the thermodynamic parameters for all the complexes indicates a common reaction mode²³. Low value of frequency factor (Z) suggests that the decomposition of polychelates can be classed as 'slow' process²⁴. In the case of the Mn^{II} chelate, the slight high values of activation energy and compensation parameter (Z) may be due to Mn^{II} having d^5 (half-filled) configuration stability, and as stability is high, the activation energy also high. Moreover, in the Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} chelates there are only four ligands attached to the central ions while in other chelates there are six ligands.

Electrical and conductance studies: The direct current electrical conductivity of polychelates were measured in their pellet form over a wide temperature range (300–520 K). In the electrical conduction domain, the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity obey the well known equation²⁵, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/KT)$, where E_a is the activation energy of electrical conduction and σ_0 is constant. This relation has been modified as²⁶: $\log \sigma = \log \sigma_0 + (-E_a)/2.303 KT$. According to this relation a plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ would be linear with a negative slope. In low temperature region the slopes of the plots have small values. This may be due to extrinsic conduction present in them²⁷, whereas in the high temperature region, a linear relationship with high value of $\log \sigma = f(10^3/T)$ has been observed. In this temperature domain, these polychelates may behave as intrinsic semiconductors²⁷. The electrical conductivity of these polychelates increases in the order: $\text{Cu} > \text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cd}$, at 100° and the activation energy of the electrical conduction increased in the order: $\text{Mn} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Cd} > \text{Zn}$. The values of electrical conductivity and activation energies (Table 1) varies with the metal ions in polychelates, which leads to the assumption of incorporation of different metal ions in the polymer²⁸.

Conclusion: The confirmation and characterisation of the compounds prepared in the present course of studies are no doubt difficult because of their insolubility and intractability. The formation as polymers from steric considerations and establishing the structure on the basis of above studies are therefore tentative. Observations of the composition of some of the compounds leads to the conclusion that they should be simple polynuclear chelates, but their extreme insolubility makes one to believe in their polymeric nature with more complex features present²⁹.

From the above studies it is concluded that the bis-

TABLE 2—THERMOANALYTICAL DATA OF THE POLYCHELATES

Compd.	Decomp. temp °C	Activation energy*		ΔS J	ΔF KJ	S^* J	Z s^{-1}	n
		FC	SW					
Mn-BMAPD	420	42.12	36.40	-309.81	138.51	-98.72	115.66	0.59
Co-BMAPD	370	27.20	24.94	-318.25	126.18	-109.92	77.68	0.55
Ni-BMAPD	390	37.69	35.98	-319.72	137.18	-109.96	81.68	0.69
Cu-BMAPD	320	19.76	19.72	-326.53	121.33	-109.38	91.07	0.74
Zn-BMAPD	310	19.50	18.80	-324.50	120.30	-108.50	85.45	0.65
Cd-BMAPD	340	24.94	26.20	-324.02	125.72	-110.51	66.48	0.63

*FC = Freeman-Carroll, SW = Sharp-Wentworth.

bidentate ligand chelates of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are of six-coordinated octahedral, Cu^{II} is square-planar, while Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} have tetrahedral geometries.

Experimental

All the metal compounds were of AnalaR grade or pure quality. The solvents were double-distilled. Thioglycolic acid and *p*-phenylenediamine (B.D.H., spectrachem) were used.

Preparation of ligand : A mixture of thioglycolic acid (0.2 mol) and *p*-phenylenediamine (0.1 mol) in MeOH (40 ml) was refluxed at 120° for 10–12 h in CO_2 atmosphere by bubbling the gas through the mixture. On cooling, the bright yellow solid was turned into yellowish brown. It was decomposed by pouring the mixture into chilled HCl solution (100 ml; 1 N). A yellowish brown solid that separated out was washed with hot distilled water, crystallised from EtOH and dried in air, (70%), m.p. 183°.

Synthesis of polychelates. General method : An equimolar solutions of metal acetate (chloride in case of Cd^{II}) and ligand BMAPD dissolved separately in minimum quantity (25–30 ml) of DMF–EtOH (4 : 1), were mixed and the mixture was refluxed at 155° for 4–5 h. The resulting solids were successively washed with DMF, dry ethanol and acetone and dried in vacuum desiccator over fused $CaCl_2$.

The metal was estimated by atomic absorption spectrometry method after decomposing the complexes with HNO_3 . The limit of detection for Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} were 0.002 ppm and for Cd^{II} it was 0.001 ppm. The metal content in each polychelate was further confirmed by oxide method¹⁹. C, H and N were analysed using a Coleman analyser. Sulphur was estimated as $BaSO_4$ by gravimetric method³⁰. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983b spectrophotometer and diffused reflectance spectra on a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer using MgO as reference. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by the Gouy method using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as the calibrant. The non-isothermal TGA measurements were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 analyser using Pt-Pt-Rh thermocouple with a heating rate of 10°min^{-1} in air atmosphere in the temperature range 25–

800° alongwith TADS computer system. D.C. electrical conductivity of the complexes was measured on a BPL (India) million megohmmeter in pellets form in the temperature range 300–500 K.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the University authorities and U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support. They are also thankful to the R.S.I.C., Nagpur University, for recording TGA. Recording of ir spectra by C.D.R.I., Lucknow, is grateful acknowledged.

References

1. B. P. BLOCK, *Inorg. Macromol. Rev.*, 1970, 1, 115; J. C. BAILAR, JR. in "Organometallic Polymers", eds. C. E. CARRANER, JR., J. E. SHEATS and C. V. PITTMAN, JR., Academic, New York, 1978, p. 313.
2. J. J. GRODZINKI, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1980, 181, 2441.
3. V. DURGAKUMARI and K. N. MUNSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 191.
4. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd ed., Methuen, London, 1958.
5. M. M. PATEL and R. MANAVALAN, *J. Macromol. Sci. Chem. (A)*, 1983, 20, 487.
6. K. NAKAMOTO and P. J. MECARITHY, "Spectroscopy and Structure of Metal Chelates Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1968.
7. N. S. BHAVE and R. B. KHART, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, 42, 977; A. S. ASWAR and N. S. BHAVE, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 1991, 269, 547.
8. H. K. GUPTA, P. L. MAURYA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 58, 218.
9. L. D. DAVE, H. K. KOTHARI and P. SUDHAMSHUMOULI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 771.
10. C. L. SHARMA and T. K. DE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 101.
11. B. T. THAKER, A. PATEL, J. LEKHADIA and P. THAKER, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, 35, 483.
12. D. K. RASTOGI and K. C. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 2219.
13. A. SYAMAL and M. R. MAURYA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1986, 16, 39.
14. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy". Elsevier, New York, 1968.
15. A. K. RANA and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 281.
16. B. SINGH, LAKSHMI and U. AGRAWAL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 2341.
17. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw Hill, New York, 1962.
18. M. N. PATEL and P. B. JANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 278.

19. A. S. ASWAR, P. J. BAHAD, A. B. PARDHI and N. S. BHAVE, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1981, **5**, 233.
20. A. V. NIKOLAVE, V. A. LOGVINEKO and L. T. MYCHINA, "Thermal Analysis", Academic, New York, 1969, Vol. 2, p. 779.
21. E. S. FREEMAN and B. CARROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 394.
22. J. B. SHARP and S. A. WENTWORTH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 2060.
23. L. D. PRABHAKAR and C. UMARANI, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 1994, **11**, 147.
24. V. INDIRA and G. PARAMESWARAN, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1987, **32**, 1151.
25. Y. Z. AHMED, S. R. SELIM, R. S. FARAG and M. E. NAWAWY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 20.
26. J. E. KATON, "Organic Semiconducting Polymers", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1968, p. 90; M. M. PATEL and R. J. MANAVALAN, *Makromol. Sci.-Chem. (A)*, 1987, **20**, 487.
27. M. SPIRATOS, G. I. RUSO, A. A. IRINEI and A. CIBOBANU, *Angew. Makromol. Chem.*, 1982, **33**, 170.
28. E. INONE, S. HATASHI, T. TALOUCHI and E. IMOTO, *Kogyo Kagalouzhni*, 1962, **55**, 1622.
29. D. BANERJEA, "Coordination Chemistry", Tata-McGraw Hill, New Delhi, 1995, p. 140; B. SINGH, P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 29.
30. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longman Green, London, 1961, p. 490.